

SOME WAYS OF ENGLISH SCIENTIFIC-TECHNICAL TERMS TRANSLATION

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Abstract. Science and technology are developing continuously because of scientific and technological revolution in cutting-edge epoch. The fields of science are growing constantly, new branches of technology are appearing and as a result of globalization. Globalization has imposed the rapid flow of scientific and technological terms [1]. The elements of vocabulary related to science, technology and production -the terminology of science and technology is active and relevant to constant updating layer of current lexis. Extra-linguistic development of terminology (development related to science and technology), profound stimulus of science and technology on human life set linguists, philologists' crucial tasks. In order to accomplish this intricate task, linguists should acquire not only general linguistic awareness of terminology, but also specific skills of terminology translation. The article considers the structural and semantic features of terminologies used scientific-technical texts and ways of translation.

Introduction. Terminology vocabulary is rising extremely quickly. Terms in any branch of science, technology and production form their own systems that have conceptual connections with professional knowledge and express these connections by means of the language. If in a common language (beyond the terminology) a word can be multivalent, then, getting into a certain terminology, it acquires unambiguity [2]. To overcome the unambiguity translators, seek the solution of the problems via modern Internet resources. They are searching for matching pairs of terms with corresponding notion in different languages. They recognize the meaning of the term through images found in many search bases. Such translation methods don't always provide desired result. There is no doubt that terminology translation plays an extremely important role so further research should be made in order to enhance the translation quality of this typology.

Literature Review. The theme under consideration deals with the proliferation of scientific and technical knowledge, which is going with new notions development, resulting in naming and coining the so-called term. Term deals with names and process of naming. Technical terms fall in two categories: general scientific and general technical terms derived from general words or terms that can be used in many fields with different meanings 2) specific (nomenclature) terms. The former one denotes general concepts of science and technology, while the latter is used in one specific field. As explained by scholars, terminology depicting a set of terms is an autonomous part of any national language that is closely related to professional activity. For example, many large companies also have their own preferred terminology, which they insist be used in all of their often-corporate documents.

In lexicological studies, terminological development issues and terminology users for communication are key importance. According to Auger there were four basic periods in the development of modern terminology. It started to originate in 1930's until 1960. From 1960-1975 the field was structured. The booming period was between 1975-1985 years. Since then the field continues expanding. Two main groups of people use terminology as a communicative tool: direct users, and intermediaries who use terminology to facilitate communication for other users. The initial one is specialists in each subject field, while the

latter is translators, interpreters and technical writers [3]. The most important problem in achieving translation equivalence of scientific and technical terminologies due to variation in the terminological difference in source and target languages. So, there is need to study the term systems and find ways to render the meaning partially or complete.

Methods. It is often difficult to find the exact equivalent in the recipient language during the translation process, so terminologies are often simply left with foreign origin in the language. So, translators have to apply the direct translation method. Direct translation involves relatively straightforward strategies which require less intervention by the translator and less deviation from the ST [4]. Leaving the terminology without translation, it should undergo certain modifications to fit into system of recipient language. The process is called adaptation of loan terminologies through interlanguage term harmonization process. It includes the following methods: The transcription/ orthographic adaptation is a formal phoneme by phoneme imitation of an original lexical unit with the help of the target language phonemes. The pronunciation of source and target languages can be the same but in writing different. Some letters in English (c,q,v,x) can be missing in target language. Such letters should conform to national alphabetic system rules. For example, office-ofis, joystick-joýstik, chip-çip, notebook-noutbuk, cartridge-kartrij etc.

Transliteration is a formal letter by letter reproduction of the original lexical unit with the help of the target language alphabet, a letter imitation of an original form of a word [3]. Transliterated words are often naturalized to assimilate the structure of the target language. Naturalization of loanwords refers to the addition of some affixes to the foreign words without changing their roots.

Calquing/ loan translation is a word (morphemes) or a phrase (lexemes) borrowed from another language by literal word-for-word or root-for-root translation. For example, *high voltage* -*yokary woltly*, ultraviolet-ultramelewşe, telegram-telegramma etc. *Semantic calques* (also known as semantic loans): additional meanings of the source word are transferred to the word with the same primary meaning in the target language. As described below, the "computer mouse" was named in English for its resemblance to the animal; many other languages have extended their own native word for "mouse" to include the computer mouse [5].

Descriptive translation and translation comments. The descriptive translation, as a rule, is used in parallel with the transcription and is applied when translating terms, culturonyms, unique objects, etc., having no lexical equivalents in the target language. The word meaning is presented with more or less common explanation. If the description as a translation method usually accompanies the word, presented in a simple form, or even is used instead of the word, the translator's comments are given beyond the text, being mentioned either in the footnotes at the same page or into the endnotes of the text. It mainly concerns various acronyms, abbreviations, and terms, "*phishing – illegal act over the internet*" etc.

Taking above-mentioned things into consideration, there are some issues in the field of scientific technical terminology and translation field. Specific requirements for the scientific and technical translation are the ability to suggest accurate terminology equivalents, which is a requirement for adequate translation. In this developing age, there is great demand to technical and scientific terms. So, today linguists/technical philologists should work in this field more than past, because it is age of technology.

Results and Discussion. In some cases, translating terms in lexical way leads some difficulties, as it demands from a translator both perceiving the original term meaning and knowledge of its possible opponents in target language. The terms can be polysemic, synonymous and homonymous. Polysemic term has more one meaning. It is widely used in

reterminologization (when a term adopts a new meaning [6]. Identifying polysemy may be challenging without sufficient technical knowledge, for example in financial terminologies, “own shares”, “debtors” and provisions are the British equivalents for American terms “treasury stock”, “accounts receivable” and “allowances [7]. A synonym is an alternate word that has the same or similar meaning of any particular word. For example, *disease/disorder, toxic: containing or being poisonous material especially when capable of causing death or serious debilitation: toxic waste a toxic radioactive gas*. One should mind, that one and the same word form can have different meanings in several branches of one and the same scientific or technological sphere. It is often encountered in homonymy. Homonymy refers to two unrelated words that look or sound the same. Two or more words become homonyms if they either sound the same (homophones), have the same spelling (homographs), or if they both homophones and homographs, but do not have related meanings. Given below are some examples of homonyms: For example: “feed” in biology -to give food to; supply with nourishment but in physics to furnish for consumption. Therefore, in scientific-technical terms translation, a translator should stick to the topic of the text to avoid the wrong versions of rendering the homonymous term. Summarizing the available research data, we have identified the following properties inherent to the terms: monosemy, specific meaning; belonging to a certain terminological system; lack of expression.

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